

MooringSense – GA 851703

Mooring System Integrity Management through Monitoring, Digital Twin and Control Technologies for Cost Reduction and Increased Efficiency

D8.4 Version 1.0

Communication Plan v3.0

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Executive Summary

This document contains the MooringSense Communication Plan, which has been designed to be in line with the definition provided by the H2020 programme and the contractual obligations. It includes the description of MooringSense communication strategy, the project visual identity and communication material.

Since communication actions and dissemination activities can overlap and make use of the same tools, the present document is complemented with the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

To allow continuous Communication Plan adaptation, the initially defined plan will be updated twice along the project duration, in Months 12 and 24. This document is the second update, corresponding to month 24.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Term	Description
B2B	Business to business
EERA	European Energy Research Alliance
EU	European Union
FOW	Floating Offshore Wind
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
H2020	Horizon 2020
INEA	Innovation and Networks Executive Agency
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
JP	Joint Programme
KOM	Kick-Off Meeting
MC	MooringSense Consortium
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OW	Offshore Wind
O&G	Oil and gas
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small and medium enterprise
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
URL	Universal Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The effective MooringSense communication requires to set strategic measures to reach a multitude of audiences beyond the project own community (e.g. industrial and scientific communities), including the media and the public in general. At this regard, it is considered of paramount importance to reach out to the European society in order show the impact and benefits of EU-funded research and innovation activities, and how MooringSense addresses societal challenges related to decarbonization and energy security, providing innovative solutions with high impact.

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of the MooringSense's Communication Plan is to define the set of actions and measures, as well as the communication material to be used in the promotion of the project and its results during the whole lifetime of the action. Three versions of the Communication Plan will be elaborated during the project. This document describes the second version of the plan.

The first version of the Communication plan covered the definition of the MooringSense communication strategy, including objectives, message and target audiences, the identification and definition of the intended communication channels and communication materials, the definition of metrics and targets to monitor de effectiveness of the communication activity and a planning of activities.

The second version provides more details on the communication plan definition and reports the main actions and achievements.

1.2 Intended audience / Classification

This document is intended for all project partners, WP leaders and WP participants. The document is also intended for use outside the project, it is therefore classified as a public document.

Relevant parts of this study can however be used in public documents.

1.3 Application documents

Inputs from the following documents were used as a source of information for preparing this document.

Table 1.1: Application documents

REF	Document
AD-01	Grant Agreement – 851703 - MooringSense
AD-02	Consortium Agreement – MooringSense

1.4 Reference documents

The following list contains references to other deliverables of the MooringSense project mentioned in the present document, where complementary information can be found.

Table 1.2: Reference documents

REF	Document
RD-01	D8.6 Communication and Dissemination Report on Activities
RD-02	D8.1 Communication Plan v1

1.5 Document structure

The document is structured in the following sections:

- Section 2 provides a brief description of the methodology.
- Section 3 describes the MooringSense communication strategy through the identification of main objectives, key message, and target audience.
- Section 4 provides detailed information about the commercial material that will be used in the project
- Section 5 details the metrics that will be used for the assessment of communication activities
- Section 6 provides the GANTT of the communication action plan

2. Methodology

In addition to dissemination of MooringSense project results, partners will make a remarkable effort to effectively communicate the project and its impacts. All the communication activities will be accomplished through a specific communication plan that will be designed and implemented within the project. This plan intends to be used by the MooringSense project partners as a guide to develop their individual and collective communication activities according to the communication strategy defined.

The communication plan described in this document comprises a wide variety of measures to ensure the fulfilment of communication objectives, as well as the definition of metrics to enable the communication success assessment.

Finally, the communication plan will be updated along the project to ensure the achievement of communication targets. Plan updates have been scheduled with the following calendar:

Figure 2.1: Communication Plan updates

3. Communication Strategy

3.1 Objectives

The communication strategy of MooringSense project has three main goals:

1. **Project traceability:** Tracing the project implies constantly and coherently communicating its development, the main milestones reached and the most relevant results. Openness has been a priority, but at the same time issues regarding IPR protection will be taken into account.
2. **Broader socialization.** Technological innovations and cost reductions achieved by the European industry has paved the way for the wind energy sector to emerge as a strategic sector for the European economy and for its growth and decarbonization. However, proactive innovation is still needed to keep the EU wind industry's competitive edge and technology innovation efforts. The socialization goals can be stated as:
 - a) EU R&I strategy and MooringSense alignment (e.g. improving operation and maintenance via digitization).
 - b) Public funding leveraged to unlock private investment in R&I.
 - c) Remove barriers regarding social acceptance of FOW.
3. **Raise awareness** of the paramount importance for Europe of wind energy, in particular the OW energy, as a strategic sector for the European economy and for the wellbeing and prosperity of European societies.

The present Communication Plan details the instruments intended to be used by the MooringSense consortium to ensure the above-mentioned goals. Communication activities will be continuously monitored and reported with detail in RD-01 (D8.6 Communication and Dissemination Report on Activities).

3.2 Key message

The key message is that the MooringSense project will help to reduce the cost associated to the production of offshore energy, enhancing the shift from production from fossil to renewable energy sources and contributing to solve the global climate and energy challenges.

Through the development of more efficient strategies and tools for mooring system integrity and control, MooringSense aims at reducing FOW operational costs by 10-15% and to increase the Annual Energy Production by 2-3%.

Key facts/ideas:

- O&M costs in FOW farms can range between 6% and 20% of the whole Life Cycle Cost depending on site conditions and the FOWT technology concept. At the same time, maintenance accounts for the largest portion of O&M effort, cost and risk.
- MooringSense will foster the shift from unscheduled maintenance to schedule maintenance, since scheduled maintenance results in reduced costs of services and optimized availability (less downtime).
- Mooring systems failure statistics in the O&G sector show unexpected high failure rates. From this data, it can be derived that there is a high degree of uncertainty related to mooring systems performance and O&M costs. Even more if we considered the higher complexity of FOWT loading conditions.
- Current control strategies are conservative and control parameters are tuned in a not coordinated way along the wind farm. On the other hand, FOWT components are sized to withstand the worst-case extreme and fatigue loads. If more holistic control strategies were developed and applied it could lead to improved operation of FOW farms and increased efficiency, since an optimal balance between loads and energy production could be reached.

3.3 Target Audience

To ensure the maximum effectiveness of the communication plan, potential interested parties have been identified and grouped, in order to address specific messages via the optimal channels:

Table 3.1: Communication targets and appropriate communication tools

Stakeholders	Objectives [Impact]	Communication Activity/Channel
General public	To raise project awareness [Low]	Visual identity; Website; Infographic video; Brochures, flyers, leaflets; Press releases; Social media: YouTube, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn.
Green organizations	To inform about environmental aspects [Medium]	
EU/International associations or platforms in the Energy Sector.	To inform about the latest advancements of research in the field [Medium]	In addition to the above mentioned channels: Public deliverables; Demonstrators; Workshops; In addition to the above mentioned channels: B2B meetings with experts and relevant stakeholders.
Governmental agencies & regulatory bodies	To have their support, as their impact is high [High]	
Scientific community	To exchange knowledge, research findings and best practices developed in related projects [High]	
Industry/SME and Advisory Board	Create potential commercialization opportunities with stakeholders [High]	

The main roles of the project target groups are as follows:

Table 3.2: Preliminary Communication Plan

Audience	General public	Green organizations	EU/International associations	Public bodies	Scientific community	Industry/SME and Advisory Board
Increase project visibility	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Give input/feedback on project development	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Generate Market opportunities	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓
Support project development	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Advance Collaboration	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

According to the different target groups and communication objectives identified, the following activities are planned:

- **Objective 1: Improving Competitiveness and Market Uptake**

To WHOM	WHY and WHAT	HOW
Industry-FOW operators and service providers	Inform potential customers about benefits and potentials of the MooringSense development and receive feedbacks from an end-user point of view	Direct contact with end-users in workshops , discussions with the industrial partners (Advisory Board), dedicated information on brochures , website, presentations in relevant European and National associations (EERA JP WIND ...), participation in exhibition events.
Industry - European OW	Increase critical mass on the market, identify potential synergies, foster wider commercialisation of results, establish cooperation relations and maximize and extend project impacts.	Dedicated workshops, conferences and brochures . Participation in EU (Wind Europe, Vanguard Initiative, EERA JP WIND and JP OCEAN) and national associations (e.g. Reoltec, Enermar, Belgian Energy Research Alliance...). MooringSense will participate actively at key conferences and exhibition EU events about Wind Energy.
Industry - Investors, Banks, Insurance	Provide awareness & means for reducing OPEX and life cycle cost efficiency.	Specific meetings with the participation of contractors/investors as Equinor, EDF, Members of the MooringSense Advisory Board: Film Ocean, DNV GL, NREL, Siemens Gamesa and Dragados Offshore in dedicated meetings.

- **Objective 2: Improving Public Perception and Societal image**

To WHOM	WHY and WHAT	HOW
General public - European citizens, Green Organizations, Public Bodies and Scientific community in general.	Make wider community aware of impact of EU research, Energy Union Strategy and the strategic targets related to OW. Improve public image of OW technology. Enable contacts with the project partners.	MooringSense website; press releases; social media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn); project dissemination material; creation of MooringSense infographic video (YouTube, exhibitions...), interviews in local media and science magazines. Links with consortium members' activities for the promotion of scientific culture and new clean energy technologies
Scientific Community - Other R&D initiatives and project consortia	Use synergies, e.g. joint resources; uptake of suitable external developments. Exchange of results in other OW projects, and cooperative work.	Networks and websites, participation in CSAs, joint workshops , cross-project partner networks, joint conferences, cooperation agreements with other H2020 projects.

Scientific Community	Attract young people; Inform about job opportunities; Improve technical skills for under- post-graduate students.	Training material, presentations at universities, twinning projects, internal placements for students, newsletters to target groups and technical public information.
Other sectors	Get information on latest development and available new solutions; Initiate cooperation with other industry sectors such as O&G, offshore aquaculture, or shipping/shipbuilding.	Desk research, networks of the MooringSense partners who are active in other synergetic sectors (e.g. Intecsea, Vicinay and Bridon-Bekaert for O&G, Sintef Ocean for aquaculture and ocean energy, and TNO for environmental issues).

- **Objective 3: Removing external barriers towards application**

To WHOM	WHY and WHAT	HOW
Cross-industry standards (ISO, Class Societies,	Transmit findings and needs of standards to increase critical mass across sectors.	Participation in meetings in standard committees on EU and national level, facing similar challenges & barriers (technical, environmental, social acceptance, etc....)
Research Administration and funding authorities	Ensure consideration of achievements and RDI needs for future research programmes.	Public deliverables and reports to EU associations, contact with national governments

4. Communication Channels and Material

4.1 Visual Identity

In line with the H2020 visual guidelines, a visual identity has been created for the project, comprising a logo and style in different formats.

The logo has been designed as a word-picture-brand, taking into account the planned usage in both printed and digital media. The logo is built around the project name, including a clear symbol of both mooring lines and floating offshore wind turbines.

It is a very recognizable and eye-catching logo, easy to identify and will ease the project identification by the public:

Figure 4.1: MooringSense logo

On the other hand, selected pantone will help the final user to identify the application environment of the developed technology as a marine application. This color palette will be applied to the different documents' templates:

Table 1 MooringSense logo Pantone

	RGB
	151; 182; 217
	106; 137; 187
	45; 77; 139

4.2 Communication Guidelines

4.2.1 INEA communication guidelines

The intention of these guidelines is to maintain coherence and uniformity in our dissemination and at the same time ensure compliance to EU requirements. These guidelines are based on the communication obligations signed on the Grant Agreement.

Mandatory (as in grant agreement)

- Before engaging in a communication activity, the beneficiaries must inform the Coordinator, that will inform the Agency.
- Communication material shall always display the EU emblem prominently. See https://europa.eu/european-union/abouteuropa/legal_notices_en for more information on the use of the European emblem;

Figure 4.2: EU emblem reproductions in black & white, 2 colours white & blue and colour reproduction

- Communication material shall always include the following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 851703

- Any communication activity must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the agency, and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

4.2.2 MooringSense additional communication guidelines

In addition to the required, recommended and optional guidelines by the Commission, the project has confirmed their own guidelines. When in doubt or in the unexpected case of conflict, Commission guidelines always have priority.

- *Notification prior to dissemination*

All communication activities will be announced prior to dissemination to the Project Coordinator at: WP8@mooringsense.com.

- *Reference to website*

All dissemination activities will refer to the website URL of the project; All project members will ensure that their communication activity or product is also recorded on the MooringSense website: www.mooringsense.eu

- *Compliance to style*

In communication activities where project members present the project or on behalf of the project, all will use the MooringSense house style as much as possible over the affiliations house style (logo, and templates)

4.3 Partners Website

All the partners will include a mention to the MooringSense project and their contribution on their respective websites:

Partner	Website publication
CTC	https://centrotecnologicoctc.com/2019/11/12/mooringsense/
SAITEC	https://www.saitec.es/en/noticias/noticia26.html
ZUNIBAL	https://zunibal.com/en/mooringsense/
TNO	https://www.tno.nl/en (*)
VICINAY	https://www.vicinaymarine.com (*)
IKERLAN	https://www.ikerlan.es/noticias
SINTEF OCEAN	https://www.sintef.no/en/ocean/offshore-wind/#News (*)
BWRI	https://www.bekaert.com (*)
INTECSEA	http://www.intecsea.com (*)

(*) In preparation on the moment of delivery of this deliverable

4.4 Project Website

One of the main communication channels of the MooringSense project is the website. The project website will serve as a central point for all public materials: links to relevant events or publications related to the project, notes about events where consortium members are participating, press releases, news on the field, documentation generated by the project like public deliverables, online versions of any leaflets or posters, and other useful material like possible videos of eventual integration tests. Besides, the main language on the website is English, which facilitates its wider diffusion in the EU.

MooringSense website is available since early March 2020 and it is organized in several sections that are explained hereinafter.

The site is structured in the following sections and with the following contents:

Table 2 MooringSense website content

HOME
Was designed to act as the main landing page of the website. Consequently, a great effort was paid in the visual design and the use of eye-catching images. Apart from the visual, this page includes key messages for the project and links: updates.

Links to other sections of the website: objectives and technology. Form to subscribe to the MooringSense newsletter.

Information about the consortium and the main technical contributions of each partners.

Links to the MooringSense videos. It can be seen that the first video is currently available:

Links to news and events

News

MooringSense lays the foundation for a model to manage the structural integrity of FOW turbine mooring systems
 18 May, 2020 by MooringSense in News

The World's Largest Floating Wind Farm Is Already Hard at Work
 5 February, 2020 by MooringSense in News

Digital Twins Mature in the North Sea
 5 February, 2020 by MooringSense in News

Events

GLOBAL OFFSHORE WIND 2020 – 16 – 17 June | Manchester Central | #RUKGOW20
 5 February, 2020 by MooringSense in Events

Attend the premier offshore wind event in the world's largest offshore wind market. Experience this exciting sector come to life over two jam-packed days of political keynotes, expert panels, debates, procurement tenders, sector deal updates, disruptive innovation, business partnering, international pavilions, inward delegations and much more.

Links to the social networks

About (about the project):

This tab is organized in three subsections:

- Project main objectives: <https://www.mooringSense.eu/objectives/>

- Technology: <https://www.mooring sense.eu/technology/>
- Consortium description (it will include main contacts for the project): <https://www.mooring sense.eu/consortium/>

MooringSense project

Includes a brief description of the project

- Indication of the Milestones
- Progress - to be updated with project current status, last achievements and next steps <https://www.mooring sense.eu/mooring-sense-stages/>

Publications

Publications tab includes the following sections:

- Communication and dissemination material
- Public deliverables: <https://www.mooring sense.eu/deliverables/>
- Scientific publications: <https://www.mooring sense.eu/scientific-publications/>
- Communication: <https://www.mooring sense.eu/communication/>

News and events

It includes:

- Agenda of congresses, events, workshops related to the MooringSense technologies <https://www.mooring sense.eu/events/>
- News linked to the project and the FOW <https://www.mooring sense.eu/news-from-project/>
- Newsletter <https://www.mooring sense.eu/newsletter/>

Contact

It includes the email address of the project coordinator (info@centrotecnologicocctc.com) and the physical address of CTC. Besides, in this tab can be found a form for suggestions that is linked to a dedicated email address (info@mooring sense.eu).

Home About MooringSense Publications News and events Contact us

Form for your suggestions

Name

Phone Email

Message

I accept the Privacy Policy

Send

Project contact

For more information about the project please contact:

 Centro Tecnológico CTC
Calle Isabel Torres, nº 1, 39011
Santander, Cantabria

 E-mail: info@centrotecnologicocctc.com

 Phone: +34 942 76 69 76

Your personal data are incorporated to files for which Centro Tecnológico CTC is responsible, with legal address in Parque Científico y Tecnológico de Cantabria (PCTC) Calle Isabel Torres nº 1, 39011 Santander, whose purposes is the management of collected data in the terms of the web site, the management of contacts, the execution of commercial communication actions and the response to enquiries and suggestions, being in any case their consent mandatory if it is not provided, we will not be able to assist your request. These data will be kept indefinitely as long as you do not request your withdrawal.
Your data will not be transferred to any entity without your prior consent.
You can exercise the rights of access, modification, limitation of treatment, deletion, portability, cancellation and revocation of the consent given, by writing a copy of your ID to the aforementioned address or to the email: info@centrotecnologicocctc.com.
In case of not seeing your rights taken care, you will also be able to submit your claim to the Spanish Agency for Data Protection.

The domain www.mooringsense.eu has been registered and the website will be fully available and fully operative on April 2020. The project's website will remain available for at least one year after project's conclusion. Then, the results will be migrated to regular parts of the web communication available to the partners.

4.5 Posters, leaflets, and document templates

As part of the communication material, diverse information tools are considered within the MooringSense project. All these elements are generated in accordance with the Communication Guidelines described in section 4.2 Communication Guidelines

First, templates for the elaboration of reports and technical presentations were developed within the first quarter of the project. Then, a first version of MooringSense's poster and leaflet were elaborated that are available since June 2020.

Figure 4.3: Initial version of the MooringSense's poster (left) and MooringSense's leaflet (right)

A second version of the poster and leaflet will be elaborated including preliminary outcomes of the project.

4.6 Newsletter

Periodic newsletters are being released to subscribers among the target groups and interested public. Subscription to the MooringSense newsletter service can be done through the project website. Newsletters content includes the following aspects:

- Project status update
- Future events where the consortium will participate
- Future events related with the project developments
- News related to the project topics

Figure 4.4: MooringSense’s first newsletter

The following news related to the MooringSense published in recent period:

MooringSense reaffirms the importance of innovation to reduce the costs of floating offshore wind

8 November, 2021 by MooringSense in News

The European MooringSense project aims to reduce operating and maintenance costs by up to 10-15% and improve the energy yield of floating wind turbines used for offshore wind power generation

MORE

MooringSense, the European Project led by CTC, spurs interest at the ENERMAR Technical Seminars

1 October, 2021 by MooringSense in News

MooringSense has caught the attention and interest of the audience attending the 11th Edition ENERMAR Technical Seminars. This event was held at the Niemeyer Centre in Avilés and conveyed the

MORE

MooringSense drives the organisation of an international workshop on offshore wind energy

23 September, 2021 by MooringSense in News

MooringSense was one of the initiatives that led to EERA, JP WIND organising the workshop called "Ongoing research in offshore wind structure" as a bonus to its Annual Event. Along

MORE

<p>MooringSense successfully advances the development of technologies to improve predictive maintenance of mooring systems</p> <p>28 June, 2021 by MooringSense in News</p> <p>The European MooringSense project is successfully advancing in developing technologies that will enable designing an efficient strategy for managing the structural integrity of mooring systems. The international research, which aims</p> <p>MORE</p>		
<p>MooringSense successfully defines the architecture of its digital twin</p> <p>4 December, 2020 by MooringSense in News</p> <p>The European MooringSense project, which aims to reduce the costs associated with floating offshore wind energy production by 10-15%, has taken a step forward in defining a more efficient management</p> <p>MORE</p>		

4.7 Social Networks

Social networks are considered to have the power to achieve a multiplier promotional effect on communication activities. Through them it is possible to stablish straight communication channels to interact with the target audience.

To make the best use of the social networks and to increase the impact of communication activity, the MooringSense consortium created profiles on the most relevant social networks. Besides, frequent posts with related news and updates on the project are being created, as an strategy to guarantee the growth of the network and to achieve the maximum impact.

Table 1 MooringSense social network profiles

Channel	Link
<p>FACEBOOK</p>	<p>https://www.facebook.com/MooringSense/</p>
<p>TWITTER</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/MooringSense</p>

LINKEDIN	<p>MooringSense Project group</p> <p>As a first step, a MooringSense group has been created. The main advantage is that we will take advantage of our professional connections to reach a bigger audience from the very beginning.</p>
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Also, the following considerations will be taken into account regarding hashtags and tags:

- **Mandatory:**
 - The use of Hashtags and tags referring to the EU is mandatory
 - The mention of the profiles of involved partners is mandatory (those having active profile).
- **Recommended:**
 - Hashtags of key words related to the publication content are recommended

The following table shows the different social networks and their direct links, as well as the different hashtags to be used:

Table 1 Summary of hashtags use policy in MooringSense

Channel	Mandatory	Recommended
FACEBOOK	#H2020 @EU_H2020 @centrotecnologicoCTC @ZunibalSL @TNOresearch @sintefocean @BridonBekaert (SAITEC, IKERLAN and INTECSEA not available)	#mooringsystems #O&M #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #integritymanagement
TWITTER	#H2020 @EU_H2020 @saitecoffshore @zunibal_SL @TNO_nieuws @IKERLAN_official @SINTEF_Ocean @INTECSEA_WP @BridonBekaert (CTC, VICINAY not available)	#mooringsystems #O&M #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #integritymanagement

LINKEDIN	#H2020 @EU_H2020 @Centro Tecnológico CTC @Saitec Offshore @Zunibal @TNO @Vicinay Marine Innovacion @IKERLAN @Sintef Ocean @Intecsea @Bridon-Bekaert The Ropes GrouP	#mooringsystems #O&M #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #sath #integritymanagement
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All the partners will follow the mentioned social networks from their respective organizational accounts and will share and recommend the content to promote the MooringSense networks.

4.8 Videos

A [YouTube channel](#) was created to allocate the MooringSense project videos. The videos will have a maximum duration of 3 minutes and will clearly inform stakeholders and the general public about the main goals of the project and its achievements. Given that the videos are intended to address a wider audience, very simple language will be used and the inclusion of subtitles will be considered to enable their diffusion during events or fairs.

At least the following videos are expected:

Video	Content	Status
1	Intended content: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project and consortium presentation - Motivation behind the project - Expected impacts 	Released in September 2020

	<p>MooringSense project 180 visualizaciones • 28 sept. 2020</p>	
<p>2</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Including Water Tank tests images planned for M22 is UNDER CONSTRUCTION. Delay of 4 months is expected due to the delay in execution of the water tank testing which has been finished at the end of the M24. <p>SINTEF</p>	<p>Target release in January 2022 (M26)</p>
<p>3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MooringSense solutions integrated and validates (M34) 	<p>-</p>

All YouTube video links will be shared using the video showcase EU service¹. By means of this service, videos are added to the EU-funded R&I projects YouTube Playlist² and also they are promoted via the social media channels (@EUScienceInnov - Twitter, Facebook, YouTube).

1 Calling all EU-funded R&I projects: <http://ec.europa.eu/research/investeuresearch/index.cfm>

2 EU-funded R&I projects Play list <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLvpwIjZTs-LjHDvRTqlyjLeflXDak5er>

Furthermore, the videos will also be shared through the social networks.

4.9 Press Releases

With the intention of rising awareness of the MooringSense project by the general public (i.e. European citizens, green organizations, public bodies and scientific community in general), as well as the FOW stakeholders, several press releases are being elaborated throughout the duration of the project.

Press releases are intended to coincide with the project meetings to provide relevant updates on the status and achievements of the project.

Press Release	Main content	Due date month
PR1	Kick off	M1
PR2	MooringSense Architecture	M7
PR3	MooringSense Specification	M12
PR4	Validated Numerical Models and Tank Testing Data	M19
PR5	Validated SHM system prototype	M24
PR6	Decision Support Tool	M30
PR7	Validated Test Execution Result	M36

Miércoles 27/1/19
EL DIARIO MONTAÑÉS

ECONOMÍA | 41

PROYECTO EUROPEO LIDERADO POR EL CTC

El consejero de Industria, Francisco Martín, presentó ayer en Copernicus el proyecto europeo MooringSense, liderado por el Centro Tecnológico CTC, que tiene como objetivo incrementar la eficiencia de los aerogeneradores instalados en el mar y conlleva un aumento del 6% de la planta. El consejero, en la foto con los miembros del 'clúster' Sea of Innovation Cantabria, aseguró que atraerá a 4,1 millones de euros de programas europeos y prevé reducir hasta un 15% el coste de los generadores eólicos 'offshore'. Cantabria cuenta con un estándar en la Feria 'WindEurope Offshore'.

MooringSense, un proyecto liderado por CTC, logra reducir el coste de aerogeneradores

D. M.

SANTANDER. El consorcio de MooringSense, un proyecto europeo liderado por el Centro Tecnológico CTC, ha alcanzado los dos primeros hitos que le permiten sentar las bases para definir un nuevo modelo de gestión de los aerogeneradores flotantes, mediante el que aspira a reducir sus costes de mantenimiento y de operación para la generación de energía eólica marina en un 15% y un 10%, respectivamente.

Los dos primeros pasos dados por el consorcio han sido identificar las principales limitaciones y carencias que presentan las tecnologías actuales asociadas a la gestión de la integridad de los sistemas de fondeo y definir el caso de referencia del proyecto que permita evaluar los desarrollos previstos de forma «realista». Seis meses después de su reunión de lanzamiento, los nuevos integrantes del consorcio han hecho balance de los progresos conseguidos.

El CTC lidera un proyecto para reducir el coste de aerogeneradores 'offshore'

La iniciativa europea MooringSense plantea una estrategia de gestión más eficiente para las plataformas eólicas flotantes

M. A. SAMPERIO

SANTANDER. El Centro Tecnológico de Cantabria sigue vertiendo proyectos tecnológicos y ha diseñado una investigación conjunta de carácter europeo que aspira a reducir hasta un 15% el coste de mantenimiento de los aerogeneradores 'offshore', así como a incrementar su eficiencia. Esta iniciativa, denominada MooringSense, se fundamenta en el desarrollo de una estrategia de gestión de la integridad de los sistemas de fondeo más eficiente para las plataformas eólicas flotantes. El proyecto no solo reducirá los costes de operación, sino que optimizará el rendimiento actual que ofrece la energía eólica flotante para aumentar la producción energética anual entre un 5 y un 10%. La reunión de lanzamiento de este proyecto, cuyo plazo de ejecución es de 36 meses, se ha celebrado ayer mañana. Será el primer resultado oficial del proyecto lo ha sido liderado por el equipo de CTC formado por María Cayula-Costa, responsable del área de Investigación y Robótica, Verónica González de Lena, responsable del área de Industria y Energía, y Alberto Prias, responsable de Desarrollo Tecnológico de CTC. La presentación pública de esta investigación se realizó el próximo 26 de noviembre en el evento WindEurope Offshore 2019 que tendrá lugar en Copernicus y contará con la presencia de Francisco Martín, consejero de Industria del Gobierno de Cantabria. Fuentes: Euzkadi, Viesky Market Investigación e Inerxia, empresas y

Miembros del consorcio que han acudido a la reunión del lanzamiento.

centros de investigación de España: INO e Inerxia, entidades de I+D+i, Sektur Wind Energy Industries de Bélgica y Sines Offshore, de Noruega, completan el consorcio de este proyecto que cuenta con más de 4 millones de euros de financiación correspondientes al programa de Investigación e Innovación Horizon 2020 de la Unión Europea.

Importante liderazgo
MooringSense es el proyecto más importante liderado por CTC hasta la fecha. El objetivo establecido por los socios implica la puesta en marcha de varias soluciones tecnológicas innovadoras. El diseño y prototipo de un armario inteligente de bajo coste para monitorizar el movimiento de las plataformas flotantes o el desarrollo de un modelo virtual de sistemas de fondeo de alta fidelidad responden sus desafíos

para los socios. Además, se conforma la definición y ejecución de técnicas de monitorización de la salud estructural (SHM), así como estrategias de control para la gestión de estos componentes.

De hecho, si MooringSense alcanza los objetivos previstos, definirá un nuevo estándar para la gestión de la integridad de los sistemas de análisis. Asimismo, se espera que los conocimientos derivados del proyecto generen varias patentes.

La puesta en marcha de este proyecto responde a una investigación multidisciplinaria respecto de la necesidad de gestionar los activos offshore de forma más eficiente para contribuir a la reducción de coste de la energía eólica flotante. Las innovaciones tecnológicas y las reducciones de costes han allanado el camino para que el sector de la energía eólica marina comience a ser estratégico para la economía cantabrita. Sin embargo, necesitan más innovaciones proactivas para mantener el liderazgo mundial en esta tecnología. Además, la reducción de los costes operativos y el incremento de la eficiencia, el proyecto energético para la economía cantabrita.

MooringSense es el cuarto proyecto europeo que lidera CTC en los últimos años.

Erwind, News Menu, offshore, Wind Energy

CTC works to reduce the cost of floating wind turbines by 15%

May 14, 2020 | revu

The MooringSense consortium, a European project led by the CTC Technology Center, has reached the first two milestones that allow it to lay the foundations for defining a new management model for floating wind turbines, by means of which it aspires to reduce its maintenance and of operation for the generation of offshore wind energy by 15% and 10%, respectively.

Figure 4.5: Publication in printed newspaper and online media through press releases in MooringSense

All partners will publish project results in local and international press: press releases, newsletters in magazines and newspapers etc. Moreover, all beneficiaries will use their own communication portals to include the main information about the project and its results.

Furthermore, the following distribution channels will be exploited by the partners to maximize the impact of the press releases generated:

- Local agencies

A list of local communication agencies will be created during the project development. Press releases will be also sent to these agencies to maximize the impact and to increase the awareness of European citizens.

- EC's media channels:

- <https://horizon-magazine.eu/>
- <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/newsroom/551/>
- <https://cordis.europa.eu/news/en>

So far, press releases linked to the kick-off meeting and the first progress meeting (May 2020) were made. The following figure shows results in both printed and online media.

4.10 Workshops

Three workshops, at least, will be organized and conducted during the course of the project. These workshops will be scheduled and organized as side events at relevant international events or at MooringSense progress meetings.

Some topics has been already identified together with tentative dates:

1. Mooring system digital twin and model testing (M18)
2. Mooring systems integrity management under risk-based approach (M24).
3. Virtual mooring line tension measurement and SHM. (M30)
4. Final workshop: MooringSense solutions, tools and impacts (M35)

Until the date only one Workshop has been released during the EERA JP WIND conference (September 2021 – Amsterdam NL) in combined presentations of IKERLAN and CTC, covering topics:

- **Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) for floating offshore wind turbines' mooring system damage detection (IKERLAN)**
- **MooringSense GNSS Smart Sensors HW/SW design (CTC)**

4.11 Publications and participation in events

Scientific publications and the participation of MooringSense's consortium in international events will be key dissemination activities. However, this kind of activities can maximize the impact of communication. A preliminary list of publications and participations in congresses is included below:

Highlights of planned dissemination channels			
Event/Journal	Countries addressed	Type of Audience	Date (planned or expected)
Floating Offshore. Wind Turbine Conference	Global	Floating Offshore Wind	2021-2023
Offshore Energy Exhibition and Conference	Europe	O&G, OW, marine energy	2021-2023
RINA - Royal Institution of Naval Architects	Europe	Marine vessels and structures	2023
OMAE Conference on Ocean, Offshore & Arctic Engineering	Global	Ocean and offshore engineering	2022
OTC - Offshore Technology Conference	Global	Offshore energy	2021
SEANERGY – Exhibition event	Global	Offshore Renewable Energy sector	2021
Wind Energy	Global		2023
Ocean Engineering. ISSN: 0029-8018	Global	Offshore platforms. Moorings	2022
Applied Ocean Research ISSN 0141-1187	Global	Floating system hydrodynamics	2023

Journal of Ocean Engineering and Marine Energy. ISSN: 2198-6452	Global	Coastal and offshore engineering, renewable energy	2023
WindEurope Conference & Exhibition	Europe	Wind Energy	2021-2023
Journal on Environmental Degradation of Materials and its Control. ISSN: 0010-938X	Global	Corrosion and its control	2022
Marine Structures. ISSN: 0951-8339	Global	Design, fabrication and O&M	2023
GPS Solutions. ISSN 1521-1886	Global	GNSS solutions	2023
The Jo. of Navigation. ISSN 1469-7785	Global	Navigation systems	2022
IAIN Institutes of Navigation	Global	Navigation systems	2023
IEEE/ION-PLANS Position Location and Navigation Symposium	Global	Navigation systems and applications	2022
ICL-GNSS Localization and GNSS	Europe	GNSS solutions and systems	2021
TORQUE	Europe	Wind Energy	2022
EERA-JP WIND	Europe	Wind Energy Association	2021-2023
ENERMAR - Wind Energy Science Conference	National - Spain	The Marine Renewable Energy Working Group	2021
WATEREYE Cluster Event	Europe	Floating Offshore Wind	2021
ADIPEC – Exhibition and Conference	Global	Oil, gas, and energy exhibition and conference	2021
World Maritime Week	Global	Naval, Fishing, Port, Oil & Gas and Ocean Renewable Energies sectors	2021

Home Wind PV CSP Energy Storage Tidal

[Flagship Event] Future of Renewables Global 2020
Dec 8, 2020 - Dec 10, 2020, Virtual Event
A Renewable World Order

Floating wind mooring shifts from steel to synthetic fibres

Sep 23, 2020

The greater use of synthetic mooring lines will lower the cost of floating wind design and installation and reduce reliability risks, mooring suppliers told Reuters Events.

Ahead of wider commercial deployment, floating wind developers are working with technology suppliers to reduce costs.

Developers are using pilot projects to adapt designs for multiple sea conditions and water depths.

Mooring systems can have a significant impact on project cost and performance, and several international consortia are studying unique designs for floating wind technology. US developer Principle Power has partnered with US government research groups and industry participants to develop new deep water mooring solutions. In Europe, a group of ocean specialists are developing new mooring solutions for floating wind farms. Backed by European Union funding, the MooringSense consortia aim to increase annual energy production (AEP) by 2 to 3% and reduce operating costs by 10%.

Floating wind groups are developing bespoke mooring solutions that aid installation and boost reliability. (Image credit: REUTERS/Jose Manuel Ribeiro)

Figure 4.6: Participation of Bridon Wire Rope Industry in the Future of Renewables Global 2020 (left). Presentation of the MooringSense project at the WindEurope Offshore in Copenhagen by CTC.

Figure 4.7: Participation of CTC at EERA JP WIND conference 16th September 2021 Amsterdam (Netherlands)

El proyecto europeo liderado por CTC, MooringSense, suscita interés en las Jornadas Técnicas ENERMAR

Figure 4.8: Participation of CTC at ENERMAR conference 1st October 2021 – Aviles (Spain)

5. Metrics

Regarding communication activity, measurable target results have been updated and presented as following:

Communication activity	Channel	Target Metric	Updated metrics from M12
Visual Identity	Logo and templates	1 of each	Done
Website	Projects Website	> 5000 visitors	1.600 visitors 2.200 pages visited (*)
Posters and Leaflets	Posters	≥ 3	1
	Pinned Leaflets	> 500 leaflets distributed	0
Newsletters	Newsletters	≥ 6	2
Social Networks	Facebook	> 200 followers > 20 posts	45 224
	Twitter	> 200 followers > 20 posts	60 223
	LinkedIn group	> 100 members > 20 posts	207 220
Videos	YouTube Channel	≥ 3	1 (another under construction)
Press Releases	Press releases in printed and web media	> 20	42
Workshops	Side/parallel events at international conferences or progress meetings	≥ 3	1
Advisory Board meetings	Side events during MooringSense progress meetings	≥ 3	-

(*) Data analysis from 1 November 2020 to 29 October 2021

